

Data Management Plan

PROJECT	
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Overview of Project

The project Intersectional Faces of Labor Organization: Solidarity and Mobilizations in Logistics in Europe (INFALA) aims to systematically examine the forms of solidarity, agency and labor organization of workers from the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region, innovating on, or departing from, more traditional class-based labor organizing. MENA workers have become increasingly present in European labor markets and are in some countries particularly visible in logistics. It aims to investigate two contrasting cases among the largest economies in Europe: Germany and Italy and taking a closer look at two gendered cases within logistics: Amazon and a last-mile delivery case with each country. Contextualizing workers within political-economic dynamics and examining nuances of their solidarity and organization is especially important considering rising far-right politics, growing labor shortages, shifting demographics and continued migration and participation of MENA labor, and migrant labor more generally, in EU economies.

INFALA has three research objectives (RO):

- 1) Develop an *analytical framework* to examine intersectionality, solidarity and agency and secondly establish the contextual foundation by mapping trajectories of MENA migration to Italy and Germany, access to labor markets, visa regimes and bi-lateral agreements of Italy and Germany especially since 2011 (RO1)
- 2) Conduct a three-layered interdisciplinary case analysis of a) the macro-(national) of Italy and Germany, b) meso-(sectoral) being logistics (Amazon and last mile delivery) and c) micro-(worker) levels (RO2)
- 3) Compare these two case studies based on analytical framework to derive larger insights regarding (trans)national solidarity and larger labor movement (RO3)

1. Data Summary

This project will utilize three key types of data: journal articles and books, publicly available secondary data and primary data based on my semi-structured interviews with workers. The combination of these types will allow me to engage with my three research objectives (see table 1).

With regards to the journal articles and books necessary to fulfill part one of RO1:

This project is based on taking an intersectional approach to labor organizing. This requires building a theoretical framework and analytical approach that engages with intersectionality, as well as, labor research for RO1. These come from a range of theoretical and disciplinary backgrounds and points ranging from industrial relations, labor studies and political economy to migration studies, sociology, and gender studies. These underpin my analysis and the rest of the project. This framework will be continuously developed and expanded, especially in light of the fieldwork and interview results with migrant workers and hence revisited at the end of the project.

With regards to re-using publicly available secondary data necessary to fulfill RO1 and RO2:

While part of RO1 is engaging with the theoretical and analytical framework on intersectionality and labor organizing, the second part of RO1 focuses on mapping out migration trajectories of MENA to Italy and Germany, access to labor markets, etc. In order to engage with this part of the RO, I must engage with publicly available secondary data that include international reports for instance from the UN and its organizations (such as the International Organization for Migration), as well as from the EU. This will allow me to grasp the international scope as well as the European context that is relevant to INFALA. This entails, however, also an engagement with publicly available secondary data from national organizations and ministries given that this project is more specifically about the case of Italy and Germany. This data is therefore also of relevance to RO2 given that it includes examining more specifically the macro-national (being Italy and Germany) and meso-sectoral level (here being the logistics sector). Useful examples of secondary data in this case include data from the *Ministero del Lavoro delle Politiche Sociali* in the case of Italy and *Bundesministerium für Migration und Flüchtlinge* in the case of Germany.

With regards to newly generated data based on my semi-structured interviews with workers necessary to fulfill the other dimension of RO2:

Given that this project centers workers' solidarity, agency and collective organization, it heavily depends on interviewing workers. This is necessary to fulfill the last dimension of RO2, namely the micro-level of the worker. The focus is on MENA workers with a regular migration and employment status at the time of the interview. In this case, I will be interviewing 10-15 workers per case. In total, I have two national cases, and two sectoral cases per national case, following a 2x2 case study model. This means: examining Amazon workers and last-mile delivery workers in Italy, and examining Amazon and last-mile delivery workers in Germany. It amounts therefore to 40-60 interviews with MENA workers.

The study will use qualitative methods, primarily semi-structured in-depth interviews, to explore the experiences, forms of solidarity, collective practices and forms of collective organization of MENA migrant workers in Italy and Germany. These are in-depth interviews, meaning they can each last 1-2 hours. These will be audio-recorded, if workers consent to

this. These will be conducted in a safe, and respectful setting chosen in consultation with participants. In certain cases, I predict the interviews will be somewhat shorter/longer.

Having completed these steps, I will then be able to proceed to RO3 which is essentially a comparison of the two cases based on the completion of RO1 and RO2 and their engagement with the data and data generation.

As explained in later sections, this data will only be available to me as a researcher and the supervisor, but will not be made publicly available. I do aim to make my research outputs accessible and findable, which depending on format, can be various points of access: meaning journal articles via open access and depositing these in repositories, and findable, accessible and free blog posts, online newspaper articles and podcasts. I hope that these will be useful also outside of academia, especially to labor organizations and unions.

Table 1 - Data Summary

	<i>Data type</i>	<i>Data source</i>	<i>URL (if available)</i>	<i>Access/reuse conditions</i>	<i>Data format and size if applicable</i>
Literature for RO1	Online journal articles, online books, physical books	Online journal databases, etc.	Depends on the article, book etc.	Depends on how the author has published it	.pdf (digital sources and copies will be prioritized), in certain cases however physical sources/books will be used
Re-used data for RO1 and RO2	online reports/ database	European Commission	for instance: https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/statistics-migration-europe_en	freely accessible, can be re-used by citing source	webpages
		European Migration Network	https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/networks/european-migration-network-emn/emn-publications/emn-annual-reports_en	freely accessible, can be re-used by citing source	pdf, one report around 7 MB
		OECD	https://www.oecd.org/en/data/datasets/oecd-databases-on-migration.html	freely accessible, can be re-used by citing source	xlsx, relatively small under 1MB
		UN: Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population and Statistics Division	https://www.un.org/development/desa/pd/content/international-migrant-stock ; https://unstats.un.org/Unsd/demographic/products/dyb/default.htm	freely accessible, can be re-used by citing source	pdf under 5MB
		International Organisation for Migration	https://www.migrationdataportal.org/data-catalogue ; https://worldmigrationreport.iom.int/msite/w	freely accessible, can be re-used by citing source	webpage; report size for example 35 MB

			mr-2024-interactive/		
		Bundesministerium für Migration und Flüchtlinge	https://www.bamf.de/EN/Themen/Statistik/statistik-node.html ; https://www.bamf.de/DE/Themen/Statistik/Asylzahlen/BundesamtInZahlen/bundesamtinzahlen-node.html	freely accessible, can be re-used by citing source	reports under 5 MB
		Ministero del Lavoro delle Politiche Sociali	https://integrazioneimmigranti.gov.it/it-it/Ricerca-news/Dettaglio-news/id/3734/Istat-popolazione-quasi-stabile-grazie-allimmigrazione	freely accessible, can be re-used by citing source	webpages, .aspx under 5MB
Newly generated data for RO2	qualitative semi-structured interviews with MENA workers	interviews for the project in both Italy and Germany		Transcripts and audio available only to the researcher/supervisor, while pseudonymized quotes will be used in research outputs	One interview estimated to be around 1GB, meaning here 40-60 GB in total (audio recordings)

I will systematically structure my data by creating main folders that separate these three types of data: one for the scholarly works, one for re-used data and one for my newly generated data. While the first will be subdivided based on foci/thematically, the other two will be subdivided into country case folders, meaning *Germany* and *Italy*. These will be further subdivided into the relative case studies, meaning *Amazon* and *last-mile delivery*. These will at first include a folder for the respective interviews and transcripts (where the interview audio recordings will be deleted once the interviews are transcribed). I will pay special attention to being concise and consistent in naming these, by including short names: <date><type><ID1><firm><country>. Date refers to the interview date, type whether interview or transcript, ID being the number given to this interview (following chronological order relative to each case), firm being AM (Amazon) or LM (Last mile), and country being where the interview was conducted, i.e. Germany (DE) or Italy (IT). Furthermore, as I will pseudonymize interviews in order to be able to quote them (see further info regarding Special Categories of Data used below in the DMP), I will also create a pseudonymization key that will be accessible to only me and the supervisor that further identifies/connects the interview numbers (considering that the gender and country of origin is relevant to the project).

2. FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

I plan on compiling a bibliography with regards to the scholarly work (meaning here journal articles and books) that are of relevance for my theoretical/analytical framework of RO1. I will make this bibliography available and accessible via a repository (such as Zenodo) in order to make the data and thereby the project more FAIR. The secondary data that I will use to fulfill RO1 and part of RO2 is necessary for establishing the context of my research, which is all based on publicly accessible data. As such, it is all based on publicly accessible data. Although the research data itself (e.g. interview recordings and transcripts) cannot be made openly available due to ethical and privacy concerns (see below section on ethics), the project's outputs—primarily open access publications—will be made findable through DOIs, deposited in repositories such as the institutional repository (IRIS <https://ricerca.sns.it/>) and I will additionally explore Zenodo. Metadata related to the research design and outputs (e.g. abstracts, keywords, funder details, ORCID IDs) will be clearly structured and standardized to support discoverability. The project will abide therefore by FAIR principles and consider these principles across all of its methods.

2.2 Making data accessible

Due to the sensitive nature of the data and the ethical obligation to protect the identities and privacy of migrant worker participants (for more see data security and ethics section), the collected interview data will not be made publicly accessible. To ensure the confidentiality and safety of participants, all interviews will only be recorded with explicit consent. If a participant prefers not to be recorded, written notes will be taken instead. Where recording is permitted, interviews will be transcribed/translated. As this project is on migrant workers and intersectional solidarities, it means by extension that this research includes special categories of personal data as outlined by the GDPR. Thus, when using quotes of workers (given that they consent to this), their quotes may be pseudonymized but I will do so in such a manner that these cannot be traced back to them. Once transcription and translation are complete—within a target timeframe of three months—the original audio recordings will be securely deleted. Transcripts will be stored securely for up to five years, after which they will be permanently deleted (all outlined in my consent sheet). These measures ensure that access to the data remains strictly restricted and fully compliant with ethical and legal standards. Although then the raw data cannot be made accessible due to participant confidentiality and GDPR, information about the data and methods will be transparently described in publications and accompanying metadata.

While the direct transcripts cannot be made accessible, I am committed to accessibility. For one I will post my bibliography for my analytical framework in a depository which will be accessible, and outputs such as podcasts, blogposts and newspaper articles will also be accessible. Most importantly, in line with Horizon Europe's open science requirements, all peer-reviewed publications resulting from the project will be made openly accessible, see more below in point 4. In cases where this all should not be possible, a machine-readable accepted version will be deposited in a repository latest at the time of publication.

2.3 Making data interoperable

My publications will be in English, and hence, accessible to a global readership. While I will conduct interviews in various languages (Arabic primarily, English and German), these will all be translated into English upon transcription and most importantly when quoting these in my articles.

Furthermore, interoperability will be ensured through the use of standardized metadata formats and controlled vocabularies where applicable. Publications and metadata will include clear documentation of research methods, thematic keywords, and standardized author and funder identifiers. Where possible, links to related publications will be included to support contextual understanding.

2.4 Increase data re-use

I plan on making my bibliography for RO1's analytical/theoretical framework available which will be of interest to other workers that are engaging with intersectional labor and intersectional labor organizing. While my primary qualitative data cannot, however, be reused due to ethical restrictions, the project will increase reuse of its findings by publishing under open licenses in addition to repositories, enabling others to read, cite, and build upon the results. Methodological descriptions within the articles will allow other researchers to replicate or adapt the research design (regarding case selection and how I approach researching migrant workers).

3. Other research outputs

I have mentioned that these include blogposts, newspaper articles and podcasts.

4. Allocation of resources

Data management support from staff at Scuola Normale Superiore (the EU host institution) is covered as part of the institution's responsibilities and does not involve additional costs to the project. While I may purchase an external hard drive to back up my data with my project money and voice recorder, there are no additional costs beyond that related to data storage and security. I will use either Google Drive or Microsoft SharePoint, both of which are free of charge with the SNS institutional email account.

To comply with Horizon Europe's open science policies, the aim is to publish all peer-reviewed articles as open access. I will prioritize publishing my work in journals that offer open access free of charge, and will identify suitable options by consulting available resources and transformative agreements signed by my institution. In certain cases, I may additionally use eligible project funds to cover fees (here gold access) and possibly pay fees using the project's overheads (cases of hybrid journals). In cases where this all should not be possible, a machine-readable accepted version will be deposited in a repository latest at the time of publication. All of these measures will ensure compliance with FAIR principles outlined above.

5. Data security

I have already obtained an institutional laptop with my MSCA funds which I use for INFALA. I have also consulted with our Data Protection Officer (DPO) and will be backing up my data and work online. After consulting with the DPO at SNS, I have been informed that I have

access to Google Drive as well as Microsoft SharePoint, both of which declare themselves as *GDPR compliant*.

As mentioned in an earlier section, in order to ensure the protection of interviewees, interviews will only be audio recorded if agreed to. In cases they wish to not be recorded, I will take notes. In cases where I receive consent to record, interviews will be transcribed/translated and pseudonymized (hence including some personal data as explained below), and immediately after, securely deleted from the digital recorder. I aim to transcribe/translate interviews within three months of their recording (in cases where interviewees provide their consent to be recorded). Upon doing so, the interview recordings will be deleted. Transcripts will be safely stored for a total of five years, and then be deleted.

Considering that my interviews entail questions that include *special categories of personal data as per GDPR* such as trade union membership and migration/racial/ethnic background, I have stricter protections in place due to its sensitive nature. I further explain these in the next part on *Ethics*. It will be accessible only through authentication and, be encrypted, additionally it will be backed up on an external hard drive that will be safely stored at SNS in Florence in a locked office cabinet in a locked office. I will follow the same process when it comes to the transcripts. These transcripts will only be accessible to me and the supervisor. Accordingly, full transcripts will not be published or shared with third parties. I will exploit the above discussed avenues to still ensure that INFALA is in line with FAIR principles.

This plan has been discussed and cleared with the DPO at SNS.

6. Ethics

In order to ensure that this project and that the primary data generated through my interviews follow ethical guidelines, **I have submitted this project to the ethical review board at SNS**. In my application, I engage with the participant selection, risk assessment, ethical representation, my positionality and reflexivity as the researcher, my data collection methods/analysis and storage and security.

Participation in this study poses **no psychological, socio-psychological, or physical risks to participants**. The research has been carefully designed to prioritize the safety and well-being of all participants, who are migrant workers. Interviews will be conducted in a sensitive, non-intrusive manner and in environments that are safe and comfortable for participants.

As per the European Commission's 'Guidance note- Research on refugees, asylum seekers and migrants' - migrants are considered vulnerable. Migrant MENA workers are in disadvantaged positions socially and economically, may experience discrimination in new countries (such as racism on a structural and societal level), may or may not speak the language of the country where they now reside (here Germany or Italy), and may have or may have not come to EU through irregular migration. They may have left their countries for reasons of political repression. With that in mind, INFALA will only include those who are at the time of its fieldwork on a **regular migration and employment status**. In doing so, I hope to mitigate harms/risks and fears that may jeopardize their mental states, trigger trauma or jeopardize their legal status in their new countries, or in their MENA country.

To mitigate possible language barriers that could affect voluntary participation, consent materials will be provided in the participants' native languages, with verbal explanations where needed. I am a native speaker in Arabic, English and German, fluent in Spanish and am learning Italian. I have already prepared the information sheets as well as consent sheets in Arabic, English and German. They will receive enough time ahead of the interviews to read these and ask all the questions they may have. This will also ensure that they make an informed decision regarding their participation. Participants will be informed of their rights, including the right to refuse to answer any question and to withdraw from the study at any time without consequences. Given that these information sheets are in part in academic and formal language, I will go through these sheets with the interviewee and break these down in more colloquial language (especially Arabic, given its different dialects). Where necessary, a translator may be hired.

I will offer the interviewees the possibility to provide written consent by signing the consent form. However, should these workers feel unsafe in doing so, given that they are migrants in possible vulnerable positions since the focus is on those who are organizing their workplace (and small possible chance of illiteracy), I will not oblige them to sign the consent sheet if they do not wish to do so. In that case, I will ask for oral consent at the beginning of the interview. As I have also drafted my interview guide in English, German and Arabic - where workers can choose which of these languages they feel most comfortable speaking. In cases they wish for another language (such as Turkish), a translator will be hired. After the interview, a short debrief will be provided, allowing participants to ask questions.

Interview questions asked will be limited to what is directly relevant for INFALA. Personal information asked to disclose will only be relevant ones (ethnicity given it is about MENA, employment situations, political views may be expressed through views on unions), whereas other information not relevant will not be asked (like genetic/biological data or sexual lifestyle). Far from asking workers to recount traumatic experiences, the focus is on ways they build solidarity through shared language, history and experiences and collective labor organization. I will not inquire about any unnecessary information regarding their migration that may hold any legal consequences for their migration status and will not put their status at any risk. Participants will be assured that their information is confidential and will not be shared with third parties.

This project focuses on the intersectional dimensions of labor organizing, certain information is relevant to the study: for instance their country of origin could relate to previous experiences of being a trade unionist, or be inspired by the Jasmine Revolution or Tahrir Revolution. At the same time, given certain gender stigmas and patriarchal structures, the sex/gender could be relevant to how migrants build support networks that help them organize. As previously mentioned, this means, however, that this data also includes some that falls under the special category of data as per GDPR. Thus, in order to maximize anonymity and confidentiality, I will pay special attention to how I process the data in order to ensure the interviewee cannot be identified. This includes the pseudonymization of interview quotes in research outputs in such ways that cannot be traced back to them. Given the special status of this data, I also have stricter protections in place due to its sensitive nature. I create a pseudonymization key that will be accessible to only me and the supervisor that further identifies/connects the interview numbers (considering that the gender and country of origin is relevant to the project).

This includes: explicit consent/ additional clarifications, only collect the necessary data for the research purpose and avoid collective excessive or unrelated personal data. As previously elaborated, I will safely store the data through authentication/encryption, restricted access, attentive to the requirements of storing this data and accessing this data (meaning authentication processes, back ups, etc.).

Finally, as a woman of color from the MENA region myself, who is a native Arabic speaker and has conducted numerous interviews with other members of the MENA community during my PhD and postdoc positions, I am culturally sensitive, historically knowledgeable and understand ongoing political-economic dynamics as well as social stigmas/gender regimes. I will additionally consult with experience, researchers and other cultural insiders to ensure the wellbeing of those interviewed and that no discrimination takes place and no harm incurs. I highly respect these humans and their dignity, and will also consult with workers with whom I build rapport to get feedback on the interviews and identify ways to more directly account and highlight their perspectives.

7. Other issues

Not applicable